

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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EVOLUTION OF THE PENSIONS IN GREAT BRITAIN

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Buyuk Britaniyadagi pensiya tizimining evolyutsiyasini ko'rib chiqiladi. O'n to'qqizinchi asrning oxirida ko'plab rivojlangan mamlakatlarda pensiya ta'minoti davlat zimmasiga og'ir yuk bo'lgan kambag'al aholining qarishi muammosi paydo bo'ldi. Buyuk Britaniya pensiya tizimida islohotlarni boshladi. Islohotlarning mohiyati pensiya ta'minoti uchun mas'uliyatni xususiy sektor xodimlari va ish beruvchilarning o'zlariga o'tkazish va shu bilan davlat byudjetlari yukini kamaytirish edi. Bundan tashqari, islohotlar ishchilar va ish beruvchilarni mehnat samaradorligini oshirish uchun sezilarli rag'batlantirishga qaratilgan edi.

Kalit so'zlar: pensiyalar, shaxsiy pensiyalar, xususiy sektor, davlat pensiyalari, keksa aholi, pensiya jamg'armalari, xususiy sektor ish beruvchilari.

Abstract: This article considers the evolution of the pension system in Great Britain. At the end of the nineteenth century, there was a problem of a large aging poor population, whose pension provision was a heavy burden on the state in many developed countries. Great Britain initiated reforms to the pension system. The essence of the reforms was to transfer responsibility for pension provision to private sector employees and employers themselves, thereby reducing the burden on public budgets. In addition, the reforms were aimed at creating significant incentives for employees and employers to improve labor efficiency.

Key words: pensions, private pensions, private sector, state pensions, aging population, pension funds, private sector employers.

Аннотация: данной статье рассматривается эволюция пенсионной системы в Великобритании. В конце XIX века во многих развитых странах возникла проблема стареющего бедного населения, пенсионное обеспечение которого легло тяжелым бременем на государство. Великобритания инициировала реформы пенсионной системы. Суть реформ заключалась в том, чтобы переложить ответственность за пенсионное обеспечение на работников частного сектора и самих работодателей, тем самым снизив нагрузку на государственные бюджеты. Кроме того, реформы были направлены на создание значительных стимулов для работников и работодателей к повышению эффективности труда.

Ключевые слова: пенсии, частные пенсии, частный сектор, государственные пенсии, старение населения, пенсионные фонды, работодатели частного сектора.

INTRODUCTION

A review of the existing literature on the topic of interest indicates that the history of the development of pensions in Great Britain goes back two centuries. Toward the end of the eighteenth century, the British government introduced pension plans for customs and excise officials, who were part of a limited circle of important servants of the British crown. Pensions were introduced to provide for the old age of government officials and to eradicate such negative phenomena.

In the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, this trend spread to private sector employers, laying the foundation for the development of occupational pensions offered by private employers. For centuries, employers have rewarded the long-term service of their employees with benefits and other acts of charity. Some scholars consider these pensions to be a distinctively British and American phenomenon. In the late nineteenth century, some number of such employer-sponsored occupational plans were introduced in continental Europe as well. Thus, employer-sponsored occupational pensions were first established by governments, manufacturing corporations, and then spread to other industries.

With the growing size of government and much later, the private sector, employers began to control the issue of employee retirement, primarily based on the interests of the organization. Initially, pensions were set at the discretion of the employer, sometimes out of paternalistic largesse, sometimes to eliminate employees who were no longer fit for work. In a later period, pensions and fixed retirement ages were introduced as a management technique to avoid personal announcements of a worker's dismissal and unfitness for work and to eliminate inequities in the distribution of pensions. Such principles were adopted in the eighteenth century in the expanding British state bureaucracy, then in the early nineteenth century in France and Prussia.

LITERATURE REVIEW OF THE TOPIC

David Blake's scientific work studied the UK pension system. In particular, based on the study of the reforms implemented in the pension system, the risks affecting pension provision, the efficiency of investing pension fund assets, the defined-contribution and defined-benefit systems of pension financing, he made proposals and recommendations on the development of non-state pension provision to ensure the financial stability of the pension system.

In the research of local economist B. Mamatov, the experience of foreign countries, in particular Singapore and South Korea, was studied in terms of increasing the efficiency of the national pension system, and proposals were developed to increase the efficiency of the national pension system.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The author used scientific abstraction, analysis, synthesis, and comparative analysis methods in the research.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The development of private pensions is inextricably linked to the development of state pensions. History suggests that those who had access to sufficient resources could choose when to retire. The majority in all nations and at all times until the recent past - worked as long as they were physically able to work, very often in low-paying jobs as their abilities declined with age. Some fortunate people had children to provide for their old age. As a consequence, much of the aging poor population was not provided with pensions by the state and the private sector.

In Britain, the reforms of state pensions, which also greatly influenced the development of private pension funds, have been carried out since 1946 in four phases:

1. Beveridge period - from 1945 to the mid-60s.
2. the Bismarck period - from 1970 to the late 80s.
3. The phase of government spending cuts - from 1980 - 1990.
4. the Shift to Redistribution phase - from 1997 to 2003.

After World War II until the mid-1960s, the state pension program reflected the goals of its founder, the "father of pensions," Sir William Beveridge. The National Insurance Act of 1946 established a universal, pay-as-you-go social insurance system with a single contribution rate and a single pension. The system provided a universal single minimum pension funded by a single rate of National Insurance contributions. The main purpose of the universal single minimum ("floor") pension program was to allow for the expansion of voluntary occupational pensions. However, by the late 1960s, only half of the UK workforce was covered by occupational pensions. This led to a situation in the late 1950s and early 1960s where there were 'two nations', i.e. those who received private pensions reflecting their lifetime earnings and those who relied entirely on a single state minimum pension. This situation led to a heated debate in political circles about the need for the state to introduce earnings-related pensions.

The second phase is called the Bismarck period. In 1975, the Social Security Act was passed, which required workers to join a new pension program called the State Earnings Related Pension Scheme, which was finally adopted in April 1978

The third phase of reform is the phase of public spending cuts. The election of British Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher significantly affected both public and private pensions. The problem of population aging, had already emerged by the end of the twentieth century. In the mid-eighties, after a review of social policy, the Conservative government led by Margaret Thatcher concluded that increasing life expectancy and declining birth rates would place an unsustainable burden on the active working part of the population, as shown in Table 1.

Indicators of population and pensioners in the UK (in thousands) ¹

Годы	1980	2000	2006	2011	2016	2021	2026
Population	56330	58886	60533	61 892	63304	64727	66002
Number of pensioners*	11410	12257	12953	14244	15249	16577	18218
Number of pensioners as a % of the total population	20,3	20,8	21,4	23	24	26	28
Economically active population	-	29061	30613	31700	33252	34802	36352
The ratio of pensioners to economically active population (in %)	-	42	42	45	46	48	50
dependency ratio		0,42	0,42	0,45	0,46	0,48	0,5

The table shows that in 1980 the total UK population was 56.330 million, in 2006 it was 60.533 million, this figure is projected to reach 61, 892 million in 2011 and 66 million in 2026. The population of retirement age was 20.3% of the total population in 1980, in 2000. - 20.8%, in 2006 - 21.4%, according to forecast data in 2026 - 28%. Thus, there is a tendency to increase the number of pensioners as a percentage of the total population. Foreign scientists have estimated that by 2050 this figure will reach 37% of the population. This means an increase in the pension burden of providing state pensions on the shoulders of workers and the state.²

Consequently, the Conservative Party reverted to the old liberal position that it was more beneficial for the state to return to providing a minimum “floor” level of pensions. The national government took several measures that simplified the conditions for workers to join private pension programs provided by employers or personal pension plans. The measures aimed to increase the role of private pension provision. This goal was finally achieved by the new Labor government led by Tony Blair, which came to power in May 1997. In 1998, statistical authorities indicated that 40% of pensions were provided by private pensions, and this figure should be increased to 60% by 2050.

The fourth stage, the shift to explicit redistribution, began in 1997. With the coming to power of Tony Blair's Labor administration, the government aimed to reduce poverty among pensioners. In April 1999 it introduced the Minimum Guaranteed Income for pensioners whose length of service was not sufficient to qualify for a single state pension.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the essence of the reforms in Great Britain is to transfer responsibility for pension provision to private sector employees and employers themselves, thereby reducing the burden on public budgets. In addition, the reforms are aimed at creating significant incentives for employees and employers to improve labor efficiency.

The history of the development of private pensions might be of great interest to developing countries. The transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to market relations has caused the need for deep structural transformations in all spheres of the economy aimed at achieving accelerated economic growth and increasing the welfare of the population on this basis. In the modern world, subject to the processes of integration and globalization, almost all developed and developing countries are trying to solve the problem of ensuring a decent standard of living for all segments of the population by reforming pension systems.

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